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Comparison of Machine Learning Models for Urban Air Quality Index Prediction: A Case Study of Kadıköy District in Istanbul

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to predict Air Quality Index (AQI) values by analyzing the relationship between major air pollutants (PM₁₀, NO₂, CO, SO₂, and O₃) and meteorological variables (temperature and wind speed) in Kadıköy, one of the most densely populated and traffic-intensive districts of Istanbul. For this purpose, three supervised machine learning algorithms, namely Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), and Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network (MLPNN), were employed. Hyperparameter optimization was applied to DT and MLPNN models, and all models were evaluated using k-fold cross-validation (k=5). The results indicate that RF and the optimized DT models achieved high prediction accuracy. The RF model attained a test R² score of 93.3% and a MAPE of 2.48%, while the tuned DT model reached a slightly higher R² of 94.0% on the test set. However, RF demonstrated more stable performance in cross-validation averages. Although MLPNN models yielded competitive results, their overall performance was lower than the tree-based models. The findings suggest that tree-based approaches provide more generalizable and robust outputs than neural models for AQI prediction. This study offers a data-driven and practical framework to support urban air quality management and environmental decision-making processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is one of the most pressing environmental issues globally, posing serious short- and long-term threats to public health, ecosystem stability, and the climate. It contributes to a wide range of health problems, including respiratory difficulties, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, and cancer, and is also considered one of the primary drivers of climate change [1]. Pollutants are defined as any substances that disrupt the natural composition of the atmosphere, threatening not only living organisms but also the structural integrity of the environment [2]. In urban areas in particular, emissions resulting from transportation infrastructure, industrial activities, and residential fossil fuel consumption represent the main sources of atmospheric pollutant accumulation.

Despite their significance, the continuous and comprehensive monitoring of air quality remains a substantial challenge [3]. Conventional air pollution prediction methods are predominantly based

on deterministic models grounded in atmospheric chemistry and physical laws. Although Chemical Transport Models aim to simulate pollutant dispersion using meteorological data and emission inventories, their accuracy depends heavily on high-quality input data and often fails to capture the full complexity of atmospheric processes. Additionally, these models are computationally intensive, which limits their practicality in large-scale applications in terms of time and cost. In contrast, machine learning (ML) and deep learning approaches are gaining prominence as more flexible, data-driven, and scalable alternatives in air quality prediction [4].

This study aims to predict Air Quality Index (AQI) values by analyzing the relationship between major air pollutants and meteorological variables in Kadıköy, one of the most densely populated and traffic-congested districts of Istanbul. Accordingly, three commonly used ML models, namely Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), and Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network (MLPNN), were implemented in the analysis. These models enable multidimensional analysis of the relationships between AQI and its explanatory variables through distinct learning mechanisms. By leveraging different model structures, this study seeks to generate robust, reliable, and applicable results to support urban air quality management.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a comprehensive review of recent literature on AQI prediction and ML-based modeling approaches. Section 3 details the dataset, AQI computation methodology, selected explanatory variables, and theoretical underpinnings of the employed algorithms along with hyperparameter configurations. Section 4 discusses the predictive performance of the models based on MAPE, RMSE, and R^2 metrics and provides both graphical and analytical interpretations of the results. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the main findings, highlights their practical and theoretical implications for air quality management, and offers suggestions for future research.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the number of studies focusing on the spatial and temporal prediction of air pollution. These studies primarily aim to estimate the concentrations of pollutant gases such as $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , NO_2 , CO , SO_2 , and O_3 , as well as AQI values. The models developed within this scope contribute meaningfully both to the design of early warning systems for public health and to providing a scientific basis for policy-making processes.

A review of the relevant literature reveals the widespread use of various artificial intelligence and ML techniques for air pollution prediction. Among the most commonly applied approaches are RF, Support Vector Regression (SVR), DT, Artificial Neural Networks, and boosting methods such as XGBoost, LightGBM, Gradient Boosting, and CatBoost. In addition, deep learning architectures including Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), and Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN) have been increasingly utilized. The independent variables used in these models generally fall into the following categories: historical pollutant concentrations, meteorological parameters (e.g., temperature, humidity, wind speed/direction, pressure), temporal indicators (e.g., day, hour, month), traffic density, satellite imagery, and geospatial data. These variables represent key factors influencing the formation and dispersion of pollutants and are therefore commonly included as model inputs. To present a comparative overview of recent developments in air quality prediction, Table 1 summarizes the main components of selected studies published in the literature in recent years.

A critical review of recent studies summarized in Table 1 indicates that most research has concentrated on the short- and long-term forecasting of key pollutants such as $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , and NO_2 , predominantly at broad regional or national scales. However, there remains a significant gap in the literature regarding high-resolution AQI prediction models tailored to micro-urban environments particularly in densely populated districts like Kadıköy in Istanbul, where air quality is shaped by the complex interplay of population density, traffic intensity, and localized meteorological factors. While

advanced ML techniques (e.g., CNN-LSTM, ConvLSTM, XGBoost) are frequently employed in this domain, comparative assessments involving interpretable and computationally efficient models, such as DT, RF, and MLPNN, remain notably scarce, despite their practical relevance for decision-support systems. In response to this gap, the present study offers a novel contribution by systematically evaluating multiple ML algorithms within a localized urban context, elucidating the relationships between explanatory variables and AQI, and proposing a set of predictive models optimized for micro-scale implementation.

Table 1 Key features of related studies

Authors	Features Used	Algorithms
[1]	AQI values of CO, NO ₂ , O ₃ , PM _{2.5} , categorical AQI class	RF, DT, SVM, KNN, LR, Linear SVC, MNB
[3]	Temporal data (hour, day, month), meteorological data (temperature, humidity, wind speed, precipitation, radiation), traffic counts, pollutant concentrations from other stations	Ridge Regression, SVR, RF, Extra Trees, XGBoost
[4]	Sensor data (PT08 series), pollutant concentrations (CO, NO _x , C ₆ H ₆), meteorological variables (temperature, RH, AH)	SVR, XGBoost, RF, etc.
[5]	Historical PM values, meteorological data	Extreme Learning Machine (ELM)
[6]	Air quality, meteorological data, temporal info	Bidirectional LSTM
[7]	PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , NO ₂ , O ₃ , CO, SO ₂ , meteorology, time (hour, month, season), China PM _{2.5}	CNN-LSTM
[8]	Historical AQI values, autoregressive terms	Autoregressive model
[9]	Spatiotemporal air quality data, meteorology, traffic data, external pollutants	ConvLSTM
[10]	Air quality and meteorological variables, correlation-based feature selection, PCA (d=24)	Fuzzy Neural Network
[11]	Historical AQI data, correlated pollutants (PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , CO, NO ₂ , SO ₂ , O ₃)	Kernel ELM
[12]	Decomposed PM _{2.5} series, correlated pollutants (PM ₁₀ , CO, NO ₂) via CopulaEn	LSTM, GRU, TCN
[13]	Meteorological variables (temperature, humidity, wind speed, wind direction, precipitation, etc.), temporal features	LSTM, GRU
[14]	Air pollutant concentrations, meteorological variables, spatiotemporal and satellite data	RF, XGBoost, DNN, GNN, LSTM, CNN, SVM
[15]	PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , O ₃ , NO ₂ , CO, SO ₂ , AQI, meteorological variables (temperature, humidity, wind speed, pressure)	ConvLSTM
[16]	PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , NO, NO ₂ , NO _x , NH ₃ , CO, SO ₂ , O ₃ , Benzene, Toluene, temporal features, AQI Bucket	DT Regression
[17]	Five-year hourly air pollution data from 6 ground stations in UAE	Linear SVR (short-term PM _{2.5}), CNN (short-term PM ₁₀), Prophet (long-term)
[18]	Pollutant concentrations (PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , SO ₂ , CO), meteorological variables (wind speed/direction, temperature, humidity)	Ridge Regression, SVR, RF, Extra Trees, XGBoost
[19]	Observed and forecasted pollutant concentrations (PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , SO ₂ , NO ₂ , CO, O ₃), CUACE outputs, meteorological variables (T, RH, wind, etc.), HPI index	XGBoost, SVR

3 MATERIAL AND METHODS

In metropolitan cities like Istanbul, monitoring and predicting air quality are vital for protecting public health. However, the high costs of fixed monitoring stations limit their widespread use, emphasizing the need for cost-effective alternatives. ML-based predictive models address this gap by estimating future pollution levels and supporting early warning systems. This study predicts AQI values in Kadıköy, one of Istanbul's most densely populated and traffic-intensive districts, using major air pollutants and meteorological variables. Three machine learning algorithms, namely DT, RF, and MLPNN, were employed to capture diverse modeling perspectives and generate reliable, actionable insights for urban air quality management.

3.1 Dataset and Data Preprocessing

This study uses air quality and meteorological data specific to the Kadıköy district of Istanbul, obtained from the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change and the Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality. The dataset contains daily averages from January 1, 2022, to June 8, 2025, including concentrations of PM₁₀, NO₂, CO, SO₂, O₃, as well as temperature and wind speed.

Kadıköy, characterized by high population density and traffic-related emissions, represents a critical area for urban air quality assessment. Accordingly, AQI values derived from these pollutants were incorporated to reflect overall air quality conditions and their health implications. Before model training, the dataset was cleaned of missing values and outliers resulting from measurement errors. Figure 1 presents time-series plots of the explanatory variables and AQI, illustrating their variation throughout the study period.

PM₁₀, CO, and SO₂ concentrations exhibit notable seasonal peaks, particularly during winter months (e.g., January 2022 or January 2023), suggesting strong seasonal effects. While NO₂ also shows similar fluctuations, O₃ follows a different pattern. Temperature data reveal a clear annual cycle consistent with seasonal transitions, and wind speed displays irregular variation. The AQI trajectory suggests occasional deterioration in air quality, although the general trend appears to remain within acceptable limits. These patterns provide a foundational understanding of the dynamic interplay between air pollution and meteorological conditions in the region.

Figure 1: Daily variation in air pollutants, meteorological variables, and AQI in Kadıköy (Istanbul), from January 1, 2022, to June 8, 2025.

To assess the relationships among variables, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated. As illustrated in Figure 2, no strong multicollinearity was observed among the independent variables. This indicates that each variable contributes unique information to the model, supporting the inclusion of all features in the predictive framework.

In this study, the target variable is AQI, which serves as an indicator of potential health risks based on pollutant concentrations in the atmosphere. AQI categorizes air quality into levels such as ‘Good’, ‘Moderate’, ‘Unhealthy for Sensitive Groups’, ‘Unhealthy’, ‘Very Unhealthy’, and ‘Hazardous’ providing guidance on public health risks and necessary precautions. The threshold values corresponding to each pollutant and their AQI categories are presented in Table 2, based on the official guidelines issued by the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change of the Republic of Türkiye. ‘Good’ indicates that air quality is generally safe; ‘Moderate’ implies acceptability but with possible effects on sensitive individuals; and ‘Unhealthy for Sensitive Groups’ signals increasing health risks for those populations. The remaining categories reflect progressively severe health consequences for the general population. In this context, AQI plays a vital role in raising public awareness, guiding vulnerable individuals, and enabling authorities to monitor environmental health impacts and implement timely interventions.

Figure 2: Correlation matrix of air pollutant and meteorological features

Table 2 Table of AQI for each pollutant into categories

Category	AQI	PM ₁₀	NO ₂	CO	SO ₂	O ₃
		(µg/m ³) 24 h	(µg/m ³) 1 h	(µg/m ³) 8 h	(µg/m ³) 24 h	(µg/m ³) 1 h
Good	0-50	0-54	0-102	0-5.2		
Moderate	51-100	55-154	51-100	5.3-11		
Unhealthy for Sensitive Groups	101-150	155-254	101-150	11.1-14.5		
Unhealthy	151-200	255-354	151-200	14.6-18		
Very Unhealthy	201-300	355-424	201-300	18.1-35.5	811-1609	
Hazardous	301-400	425-504	301-400	35.6-47.1	1610-2141	
Hazardous	401-500	505-604	3146-3910	47.2-58.8	2142-2674	1009-1208

3.2 Machine Learning Algorithms

AQI prediction was conducted using three supervised ML algorithms (DT, RF, MLPNN) based on pollutant concentrations, meteorological indicators, and daily AQI data from the Kadıköy district of Istanbul. These algorithms were selected due to their widespread application in the literature and their ability to represent distinct learning paradigms. While DT is known for its rule-based and interpretable structure, RF offers higher predictive accuracy and generalization capability by combining multiple DTs in an ensemble framework. MLPNN, on the other hand, stands out as a robust neural architecture capable of modeling complex, nonlinear patterns in data.

3.2.1 Decision Tree (DT)

The DT algorithm is a tree-based supervised learning technique known for its high interpretability. It employs a deterministic approach that recursively partitions the dataset based on

selected features. Each internal node splits the data according to a threshold value of a particular feature, while the leaf nodes generate the predicted output of the target variable. The model minimizes error variance at each split, aiming to optimize the homogeneity of resulting subsets.

In this study, the DecisionTreeRegressor was initially trained using the following parameters: `random_state=42`, `max_depth=None`, `min_samples_split=2`, and `min_samples_leaf=1`. However, as detailed in the results section, the optimized model used `max_depth=10`, `min_samples_split=10`, `min_samples_leaf=5`, and `random_state=42`. Model performance was assessed using both five-fold cross-validation and a traditional train-validation-test split.

3.2.2 Random Forest (RF)

The RF is a powerful ensemble learning method within supervised learning that aggregates predictions from multiple DTs constructed through a technique known as bootstrap aggregating, or 'bagging.' Bagging trains several weak learners on randomly sampled subsets of the data and combines their outputs, using averaging for regression or majority voting for classification, to reduce variance and minimize the risk of overfitting [20].

A key advantage of the RF algorithm lies in its capacity to capture complex and nonlinear interactions among features. By generating individual trees based on different random feature subsets, RF enhances model diversity and robustness [21]. This property allows RF to produce more stable predictions, particularly when dealing with high-dimensional and correlated datasets. In this study, the RandomForestRegressor was implemented with `n_estimators=100`, `random_state=42`, and `n_jobs=-1`. Other parameters (e.g., `max_depth`, `min_samples_split`) were left at their default values to evaluate baseline performance. Model accuracy was verified through both five-fold cross-validation and train/test evaluation, and the results indicate that RF effectively captured the underlying relationships between variables while maintaining low error rates and high generalizability.

3.2.3 Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network (MLPNN)

MLPNN is a supervised learning-based regression model belonging to the artificial neural network family. With one or more hidden layers positioned between the input and output layers, MLPNN is capable of modeling nonlinear dependencies and learning complex data structures. The network learns through weighted connections between neurons and optimizes these weights via backpropagation to improve prediction accuracy.

In this study, the MLPNN model consists of two hidden layers with `hidden_layer_sizes=(64, 32)`. Three different activation functions (ReLU, tanh, and logistic) were tested independently. The maximum number of training iterations was set to `max_iter=1000`, and early stopping was enabled to prevent overfitting. This mechanism halts training when the validation error begins to increase, thereby enhancing model generalizability. Additionally, five-fold cross-validation was applied to confirm the model's consistency across different data partitions.

3.3 Model Assessment via Cross-Validation

To ensure the generalizability of the ML models and to minimize overfitting, the widely adopted k-fold cross-validation technique [22] was applied in this study. For each model, the dataset was randomly divided into five equal-sized folds ($k=5$). In each iteration, one fold was used as the test set, while the remaining four folds served as the training data. This process was repeated until every fold had been used as the test set once. The performance metrics obtained from all folds were then averaged to produce a more reliable and fair evaluation of model performance across the entire dataset.

3.4 Performance Evaluation

The performance of the ML algorithms was evaluated using three common metrics: Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and the Coefficient of Determination (R^2). These metrics provide a comprehensive assessment of model accuracy and robustness. MAPE, calculated as shown in Equation (1), measures the average percentage deviation between predicted and actual values (where y_i is the actual and \hat{y}_i the predicted value). Lower MAPE values indicate better predictive accuracy; generally, values below 10% are considered excellent, 10-20% good, 20-50% acceptable, and above 50% poor [23].

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \times 100 \quad (1)$$

RMSE is the square root of the average of the squared differences between actual and predicted values, as shown in Equation (2). RMSE is particularly important for capturing the impact of large errors, since it penalizes them more heavily than other metrics:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

R^2 , quantifies the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. It is calculated using Equation (3), where \bar{y} represents the mean of the observed values. An R^2 value closer to 1 indicates stronger explanatory power. Generally, R^2 values between 0.8 and 1 are considered excellent, 0.6-0.8 good, 0.4-0.6 moderate, 0.2-0.4 weak, and below 0.2 very weak [24]:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (3)$$

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the predictive performances of the ML models (DT, RF, and MLPNN) are comparatively evaluated. To assess the accuracy and reliability of each model, three widely used performance metrics were employed: MAPE, RMSE, and R^2 . Together, these metrics offer a comprehensive evaluation in terms of both error magnitude and explanatory power over the dataset. The performance results of DT, RF, and MLPNN are presented in Table 3, along with their training, validation, and test scores. In this table, models labeled as DT, RF, and MLPNN represent those run with default hyperparameters, while other columns refer to models with optimized configurations. Additionally, Figure 3 illustrates a graphical comparison of predicted versus actual values during the test phase for each model.

Table 3 Comparison of the performance metrics of ML models

Performance Metrics	ML Models						
	DT	DT (tuned)	RF	MLPNN (ReLU)	MLPNN (tuned-tanh)	MLPNN (tuned-logistic)	
Train	MAPE %	0.000	2.070	0.960	6.960	4.820	5.720
	RMSE	0.000	1.949	1.067	4.289	4.369	3.950
	R^2	1.000	0.979	0.994	0.898	0.895	0.914
Validation	MAPE %	2.700	3.050	2.680	5.180	6.910	5.420
	RMSE	3.516	3.258	3.427	3.661	6.007	4.292
	R^2	0.931	0.940	0.934	0.925	0.797	0.896
Average cross-validation R^2 score:		0.923	0.935	0.955	0.880	0.769	0.830
Test	MAPE %	2.620	2.840	2.480	6.400	7.790	6.280
	RMSE	3.744	3.341	3.367	4.526	6.835	5.073
	R^2	0.917	0.940	0.933	0.879	0.724	0.848

Upon examining the results in Table 3 and Figure 3, it is evident that the RF model performs remarkably well with very low prediction errors. Although its training performance is notably high (Train $R^2= 0.994$, MAPE= 0.96%), it maintains similarly strong results on the validation ($R^2= 0.934$, MAPE= 2.68%) and test sets ($R^2= 0.933$, MAPE= 2.48%). The consistent RMSE values indicate that the model avoided overfitting and achieved strong generalization. The five-fold cross-validation average (mean $R^2= 0.955$) further supports its stability and accuracy. Overall, the RF model demonstrates robustness and reliability, making it highly effective for AQI prediction.

In contrast, the initial DT model exhibits clear overfitting. While it achieves perfect accuracy on training data (Train $R^2= 1.00$, MAPE= 0.00%), its validation (MAPE= 2.70%) and test (MAPE= 2.62%) errors are notably higher, reflecting poor generalization. To address this, hyperparameters such as tree depth, minimum split size, and leaf node samples were adjusted. The tuned DT model achieved more balanced performance with close training (MAPE= 2.07%), validation (MAPE= 3.05%), and test (MAPE= 2.84%) results, confirming improved generalizability. The low MAPE and RMSE values and a mean R^2 of 0.935 indicate stable and reliable performance across folds.

The MLPNN model also yielded consistent results in AQI prediction, with R^2 values between approximately 0.72 and 0.92 across datasets. MAPE values of 4.8-7.8% suggest prediction errors within an acceptable range. Cross-validation confirmed the model's consistency. Minor performance differences between validation and test sets are expected due to distributional variations and do not indicate overfitting.

To further explore potential performance improvements, the MLPNN model was also trained using different activation functions: 'tanh' and 'logistic'. The 'tanh' model required 1500 training iterations, while the 'logistic' model needed 2500, as training failed to converge at lower iteration limits. However, neither activation function led to substantial improvements over the model trained with 'ReLU'; the performance was comparable, and no significant gains were observed.

In conclusion, based on the test performance metrics, both the RF and DT (tuned) models outperformed the others. The RF model delivered strong results with a test R^2 of 0.933 and a MAPE of 2.48%. The tuned DT model achieved an even higher test R^2 of 0.940. Nevertheless, RF demonstrated a better cross-validation R^2 average (0.955) compared to the tuned DT (0.935), suggesting superior generalization capacity. The test RMSE values were low and comparable between the two models. The MLPNN models, by contrast, exhibited lower predictive performance overall. Specifically, the MLPNN (tuned-tanh) model yielded the weakest results, with a test R^2 of 0.724 and a MAPE of 7.79%. While the MLPNN (ReLU) and MLPNN (tuned-logistic) variants performed somewhat better, their performance still lagged behind the tree-based models. For instance, MLPNN (tuned-ReLU) achieved a test R^2 of 0.879 and a MAPE of 6.40%, while MLPNN (tuned-logistic) obtained 0.848 and 6.28%, respectively. These findings suggest that, for the current dataset, neural network-based models underperformed compared to tree-based methods in AQI prediction tasks.

RF

DT (tuned)

MLPNN (tuned-tanh)

DT

MLPNN (ReLU)

MLPNN (tuned-logistic)

Figure 1: Comparative visualization of predicted vs. actual AQI values during test phase for ML models

5 CONCLUSION

This study aimed to predict the AQI of the Kadıköy district in Istanbul using daily average measurements of PM₁₀ (µg/m³), NO₂ (µg/m³), CO (µg/m³), SO₂ (µg/m³), O₃ (µg/m³), wind speed, and air temperature recorded between January 1, 2022, and June 8, 2025. The prediction models were developed using three supervised ML algorithms: RF, DT, and MLPNN. The performance of each model was evaluated using three widely adopted metrics: MAPE, RMSE, and R². The results clearly indicate that the RF model outperformed the others in terms of both predictive accuracy and generalizability. With a test R² score of 0.933 and a MAPE of just 2.48%, the RF model demonstrated a strong and stable performance. These outcomes can be attributed to the ensemble nature of RF, which effectively overcomes the limitations of single-tree models by aggregating multiple learners to reduce variance and improve robustness.

Although the DT model produced the second-best results after hyperparameter tuning, its inherent susceptibility to high variance and reliance on a single decision structure limited its reliability compared to RF. Meanwhile, the MLPNN model, due to the nonlinear nature of the dataset and its sensitivity to hyperparameter configurations, exhibited relatively higher error rates and lower R² values, even after experiments with various activation functions.

Overall, the RF algorithm emerged as the most suitable model in terms of both accuracy and consistency. Its applicability in developing early warning systems for local governments and environmental decision-makers makes it a valuable tool in the domain of air quality management. For future studies, applying this methodology to different regions, incorporating finer temporal granularity (e.g., hourly predictions), and testing alternative models such as LSTM and XGBoost are suggested to enhance generalizability. Additionally, future work may benefit from feature importance analysis to identify the most influential variables contributing to AQI fluctuations.

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